

PHYTOCHEMICAL PROFILE, TOXICOLOGICAL PROPERTIES, ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY, AND TRADITIONAL MEDICINAL USES OF *Rhazya stricta* Decne.: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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Abstract

Rhazya stricta Decne. is a significant medicinal plant widely utilized as an indigenous herbal remedy. Leaf extracts possess greater antioxidant activity and are associated with higher levels of polyphenols and flavonoids. In countries such as Pakistan, Afghanistan, India and Iran. Research aimed to conduct a review of *Rhazya stricta* possesses phytochemical, pharmacological, and toxicological qualities. It is widely used in medicine and contains several secondary metabolites such as alkaloids and flavonoids, responsible for its antioxidant, antimicrobial, antidiabetic and anticancer properties. Leaf extracts possess greater antioxidant activity and are associated with higher levels of polyphenols and flavonoids. The results are discussed in the context of existing literature highlighting their scientific and medicinal significance.

INTRODUCTION

Rhazya stricta Decne. is a plant from the *Rhazya* genus that belongs to the Apocynaceae family. This family, first detailed by (Endress & Bruyns, 2000). Comprises a diverse range of flowering plants, including trees and shrubs, encompassing approximately 348 genera, primarily distributed across warm and temperate regions. Many members of the Apocynaceae family are known for producing bioactive natural compounds, particularly cardiac glycosides and alkaloids, which possess a range of pharmacological effects. The genus *Rhazya* was first recognized in 1835. *Rhazya stricta* is a small, perennial foliage a

certain 3 the year and is predominantly found in subtropical regions, such as India, Pakistan, and the Arabian Peninsula (AlNasr, 2020; Malik et al.). The genus *Rhazya stricta* was named after the Muslim scientist Abu Bakr Mohammad bin Zakariya Ar-Razi (925), who is known in Europe mainly by his Latinized name, Rhazes. This plant is also called as harmal in Pashto (Baeshen et al., 2015). The present investigation, in the case of *Rhazya stricta*, grown under different ecotype regimes compared to the reported one, needs further investigation. This plant species prefers stress tolerant, silty, and sandy soils, and the

unique climate of the Arabian Peninsula likely supports the production of fresh alkaloids with unique molecular structures (Bukhari et al.). In Saudi Arabia, *Rhazya stricta* leaves are used in folk medicine to cure syphilis, chronic rheumatism, and general body pain. (Albeshri, 2022). Indigenous healers also use this plant to treat diabetes, inflammatory diseases, helminthiasis, and sore throats (Razzaq et al.).

Folk Medicinal Uses

In Saudi Arabia, the leaves of *Rhazya stricta* have a long history of use in the treatment of syphilis, chronic rheumatism, and generalised body pain (Bhadane et al., 2018). It is also used in the treatment of diseases such as diabetes, inflammatory diseases, helminthiasis, and sore throats. In Pakistan, extracts of *Rhazya stricta* are applied to treat acne and pimples, while fresh leaves are placed in footwear to reduce foot burn and help alleviate rheumatic issues. Omani healers utilize *Rhazya stricta* for various ailments, including chest pain, conjunctivitis, and constipation (Weber, 2011). The leaves are dried and turned into a powder, which is kept in the mouth for a while to treat mouth blisters. The powder of the roots is used to treat tooth infections. Leaves and fruits are used to relieve body itching. *Rhazya stricta* plants are extracted mainly for their medicinal properties. Blood glucose levels in rats, while also increasing insulin levels, were measured 2 and 4 hours after oral administration of the drugs (Baeshen et al., 2015). Further, Treatment of various diseases: *Rhazya stricta* is a significant medicinal plant widely utilized as an indigenous herbal remedy in countries involved India, Pakistan, Afghanistan, Qatar, the United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia, Iraq, and Iran (Bukhari et al.). It is employed for various therapeutic purposes, including chemoprevention, antifungal treatment of different types of diseases, diabetes management, tumor and cancer treatment, pain relief, sedation, and as an anti-rheumatic agent (Iram et al., 2017). The identify of *Rhazya stricta* leaf traditionally applied to treat various disorders, including inflammation and Helminthiasis. Both the roots and leaves are valuable for addressing conditions such as mouth blisters, jaundice, dysentery, general debility, diabetes mellitus and tumors. *Rhazya stricta* is a traditional medicinal used to treatment syphilis

and sore throat (Al Maharooqi et al., 2016). And for problems such as puffy eyes, smallpox dermatitis, stomach pains, yellowing of the eyes, a low number of red blood cells, parasites in the digestive system (including both round and flat worms), and hemorrhoids. This medicinal plant is widely used in Saudi Arabia to treat cancer, diabetes, rheumatic pain, and skin problems. It is regarded as one of the valuable medicinal plants in Saudi Arabia, commonly used in the treatment of cancer, diabetes, rheumatic pain, and a wide range of skin disorders. It is used as a component of a supra-regional remedy to get rid of worms and as a natural laxative.

Phytochemical

Phytochemicals analysis of *Rhazya stricta* showed abundant bioactive molecules in leaves, stem, root and fruits (Atta-Ur-Rahman et al., 1989). These consist of alkaloids, glycosides, triterpenes, flavonoids, and tannins (Bashen et al., 2009). The plant contains an exceptionally high amount of indole alkaloids, which are well recognised for their diverse biological and pharmacological properties. Different kind of solvents was found to extract these secondary metabolites; among which, methanol for polar and water for hydrophilic constituents were the good more efficient . These compounds have been reported to exhibit hypotensive, antimicrobial, central nervous system stimulant, and antitumor activities. More than 100 alkaloids have been isolated from the plant (Baeshen et al., 2015) The phytochemical constituents of *Rhazya stricta* have been extensively studied across its leaves, fruits, legumes, and roots. *Rhazya stricta* roots involves a several of compounds such as glucoside, triterpenes, tannins and alkaloids (Baeshen et al., 2009). *Rhazya stricta* ,s biological effects are identification as a rich source of indole alkaloids, which are known for their diverse properties. Using various resolvents enables the extraction of a diverse range of secondary metabolites. Methanol effectively extracts water contain both polar and semi-polar molecules targets hydrophilic compounds. The screening utilized specialised reagents that react with different secondary meta. These compounds have demonstrated properties such as lowering blood pressure, fighting microbial infections, combating tumors, and acting as stimulants for

the central nervous system (Baeshen et al., 2012). phytochemical analysis have identified nearly 100 distinct alkaloids. These alkaloids multiple pharmacological activities . *Rhazya stricta* more than 100 alkaloids identified from the roots, stem, leaves, and legumes are isolated (Kim et al., 2012).

Antioxidant activity

Rhazya stricta extract are antioxidants. Methanolic extract elevated GSH and decrease lipid peroxidation in rats treated with them, thus demonstrated potent antioxidant properties (Ali et al., 2000). *Rhazya stricta* extract are more efficient in scavenging free radicals compared to synthetic antioxidant such as tocopherol and butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA) (Iqbal et al., 2006). Subsequent studies have shown inhibitory activities against lipoxygenase and acetylcholinesterase enzymes, suggesting anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective properties (Sultana & Khalid, 2010). Leaf extract form different locations (Riyadh vs western Saudi Arabia) exhibited varying antioxidant potential due to climatic differences (Mahmood et al., 2020). Root extracts and reported IC₅₀ value in the range of 400- 776 ug / mL , which supports the scavenging activity similarly, the antioxidant potential of silver nanoparticles synthesised using the extract of *Rhazya stricta* was also elevated as a probable result of the ability of silver ions to associate with and scavenge the free radicals. These extracts were abundant in flavonoids polyphenols, and terpenoids, which are known for their antioxidant properties.

Rhazya stricta extract has antioxidant action in rats, increasing glutathione levels and decrease lipid peroxidation (Ali et al., 2000). In comparison to tocopherol and synthesis antioxidant like butylated hydroxyanisole, the methanolic extract of *Rhazya stricta* proves to be a powerful natural antioxidant, exhibiting strong abilities to neutralize free radicals and anion radicals (Iqbal et al., 2006). The ethanolic extract of *Rhazya stricta* fruit exhibited notable inhibitory effects on both lipoxygenase and acetylcholinesterase enzymes (Sultana & Khalid, 2010). To assess how climate conditions affect *Rhazya stricta*, leaf samples were collected from plants in Riyadh and the western region and then subjected to extraction for analysis. BoBoth

extracts showed *Rhazya stricta* leaves from the western region in terms of antioxidant activity, as evidence by six assessment of superoxide radicals scavenging and hydrogen peroxide neutralisation (Bukhari et al.). We examined antioxidant root extract form *Rhazya stricta* .

Root extract of *Rhazya stricta* and the organic fractions isolated as soluble part following solvent extraction exhibited highly active the IC₅₀ values (g/mL) for free scavenging activity were 400 and 776. We examined the antioxidant activity root extracts from *Rhazya stricta* demonstrated by the DPPH assay (Flieger et al., 2021). Inhibition percentage of activity was calculated with the following formula: $AOAe/Ao+100$, where Ao and Ae are the absorbance measured in the absence of the extract and the presence of the extract, respectively. According to our study, both the raw extract and the resynthesized silver nanoparticles demonstrated antioxidant properties by scavenging free radicals. Indeed, AgNPs showed greater DPPH scavenging activity compared to the raw extract, which is likely due to the potent antioxidant properties of silver ions. These ions neutralize free radicals by interacting with them; the crude the extract contains phytochemical such as polyphenols, flavonoids, and terpenoids, which are antioxidant and can neutralise freeradicals. The leaf extract of *Rhazya stricta* was reported to possess antioxidant activity in rats (Ali et al., 2000). The methanolic extract of harmal leaves had the highest total phenolic content and antioxidant activity comparable to those of previously researched powerful antioxidant (Iqbal et al., 2006). *Rhazya stricta* fruits have a crude ethanolic extract demonstrated notable lipoxygenase and acetylcholinesterase inhibitory activities, supporting its potential anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective properties (Nighat Sultana & Khalid, 2010).

Antidiabetic activity:

Rhazya stricta had no significant effect on glucose levels after oral glucose treatment in both normal and diabetic rats. Dministration of *Rhazya stricta* in the water supply over a 3-7 days period did not influence glucose homeostasis parameters, such as plasma glucose levels, body weight, food and water consumption, and blood

fructosamine, in either normal or diabetic subjects throughout the study (Wasfi et al., 1994). A single dose of freeze-dried lyophilized *Rhazya stricta* extract to rats at 4g/kg resulted in a notable rise in insulin levels. Additionally, administering *Rhazya stricta* at 8g/kg in a continuous investigation of rats and mice, glucose (1g/kg) was supplied orally to diabetes rats caused by streptozotocin. For 28 days, *Rhazya stricta* loophole extract had no effect the glucose or insulin levels, nor did it cause any significant changes in other blood parameters, chemical, or hematological factors (Tanira et al., 1996). *Rhazya stricta* extract was given to diabetes-prone rats in the amounts of 0.5, 0.5, 2.0, and 4.0 grams per kg through the mouth, resulting in a shows a considerable drop in glucose levels after one hour (2 and 4 grams per kg) at the dose. Daily administration of the leaf extract at dosages of 0.5, 2, and 4g/ kg reduction glucose levels by 6%, 8%, and 30% on consecutive days (Ali et al., 2000). *Rhazya stricta* extract may help cure diabetes by increasing adiponectin levels, as it helps increase the levels of this hormone (Baeshen et al., 2010). *Rhazya stricta* root extract inhibited DPP-DPP-IV enzyme by up to 83%, indicating strong antidiabetic action. GLP-1 secretion plays a critical role in glucose control, which plays a crucial role in glucose regulation (Mahmood et al., 2020). In both fasting and non- fasting situations, the ethylacetate component of *Rhazya stricta* leaves is the most effective at lowering blood glucose levels. Its effective on glucose lowering is comparable to that of glucophage (metformin), a standard antidiabetic medication. This was demonstrated in studies on hyperglycemic mice, where the ethyl acetate extracts significantly lowered blood glucose levels to levels comparable to those achieved by Glucophage. This suggests strong potential for the ethyl acetate fraction of *Rhazya stricta* plays a role in the development of anti-diabetic medicines. DNA barcoding is a technique for identifying plant species by analysing a specific section of their DNA (Kress & Erickson, 2007). The region studied DNA barcoding, including both coding and noncoding sequences from the plastid and nuclear genomes. Key plastid genome regions are the coding intergenic spacers such as PSbA-trnH and trnlnrf. From the nuclear genome,

commonly examined regions include the 16S, 18S, and internal transcribed spacer (ITS) regions (Gupta et al., 2022). These initiatives have identified several chloroplast DNA loci, including mat, rbcL, rpoB, and rpoC1, as well as the psbK-psbL and atpF- atpH intergenic spacers, are showing the ability to identifying medicinal plants reliably. The MatK region was selected as an acceptable barcode for flowering plants (Lahaye et al., 2008). The positive outcomes were achieved Rauvolfioideae is a subfamily of the Apocyanacea plant family (Patil et al.). rbcL has been proposed for effective species identification. Given the proven success in amplification and sequencing (Kress & Erickson, 2007). Furthermore, the use of rbcL sequences resolved classification uncertainties within Cupressaceae, Cornaceae, Ericaceae, and Geraniaceae specimens. The analysis accurately identifies *Ochradenus arabicus*. They recommended using this marker together with the marker for DNA barcoding. It has been proposed that using only one DNA barcode locus may not offer enough genetic diversity to discriminate among closely related taxa (Kress & Erickson, 2007). The intergenic spacer between atpF and atpH helps validate medicinal plant material, as it can discriminate species based on amplicon length polymorphism and sequence variation. It has been successfully used to differentiate closely related medicinal plants and detect adulterants without requiring sequencing, making it a practical marker for species identification in herbal products. Additionally, when combined with various regions, like psbk-psbl and atpFatpH, atpF-atpH improves the accuracy of DNA barcoding for medicinal plants, including *Rhazya stricta* (Tehen et al., 2014). To differentiate the intergenic spacer psbK-psbl has been examined as a possible candidate for plant DNA barcoding, with the rich flora of Kruger National Park, South Africa, serving as a model system (Lahaye et al., 2008). This region exhibits higher sequence variability compared to many coding genes, which enhances its ability to differentiate closely related species. Although psbk psbl alone shows good discriminatory power, studies suggest that combining it with other markers, like matk and trnHpsbA, only slightly improves species identification rates. Consequently, some researchers commend focusing on a single, well performing barcode,

such as mark for plants, rather than multiple regions. Toxicity studies of *Rhazya stricta* : *Rhazya stricta* leaves were tested for toxicity in Najdi lambs by oral administration at a dose of 1g/kg/day. The lambs exhibited symptoms including weight loss, ruminal bloating, diarrhea, difficulty breathing, and weakness in the hind lambs. Protein, albumin, and calcium levels, as well as leucopenia and anaemia, were related with kidney disease, pulmonary oedema, internal haemorrhaging, elevated serum levels of AST and LDH, increased bilirubin and urea, decreased injury, lymphocyte infiltration in key organs, and cardiac blood vessel congestion. A significant drop in total white blood cells was observed in adult albino rats following intraperitoneal administration of *Rhazya stricta* extract at 15mg/ kg body weight. An intraavenous dose of 80mg/kg of the determine resulted in a 50-60% reduction in blood cell count within three days, followed by respiratory depression, convulsions, and death. The count returned to normal levels after 7-10 days. The oral median lethal dose (LD50) of *Rhazya stricta* extract in mice was established at 16.0g/kg. Even at considerably elevated doses, the extract did not induce death and exhibited no noticeable toxic effects (Ali et al., 1995). A different investigation reported that administering *Rhazya strica* extract at concentrations of 0.5-2g/kg/day for three days during pregnancy did not cause any significant malformations in rat fetuses. Apart from an overall reduction in growth, no skeletal deformities were observed. Higher doses (5 or 8g/kg/day for three full days reduced the amount of visible fetuses and impaired embryonic development, which may have contributed to abnormalities and fetal deaths (Rasheed et al., 1997).

Antimicrobial:

The vast array of plant species worldwide offers promising opportunities for discovering and developing novel antimicrobial agents. The World Health Organisation (WHO) states that around 80% of the population in underdeveloped nation still relies on traditional medicines derived from medicinal plants. The total amount of known vaious kinds of plant is estimated to about 374,000 (Christenhusz & Byng, 2016), compared to the 28,187 plant

species utilized by humans for medicinal purposes. The World Health Organization has catalogued more than 20,000 medicinal plant species, highlighting their importance as a valuable resource for developing new pharmaceuticals. Medicinal plants are recognised as valuable sources for discovering new pharmaceutical compounds. They provide a rich diversity of bioactive substances that serve as leads for drug development. This potential is supported by their historical use and ongoing research, which combines botanical, chemical, and pharmacological methods to identify novel therapeutic agents. Over 100 countries have established regulations governing medicinal plan. The present, there are almost 1340 plants. Over 30,000 antibacterial chemicals have been isolated from these plants (Tajkarimi et al., 2010).

Natural anti-microbial compounds can work alone or synergistically with anti-biotics to improve effectiveness against a wide range of bacteria. To accurately assess the effectiveness of promising medicinal plants and confirm their antimicrobial value, the data collected must be reliable, thorough and rigorously validated. Obtain an extensive understanding a more thorough understanding of the prospective application of medicinal plant extracts as alternative agents against drug resistance, this review critically examined key studies on several aspects, the validation of antimicrobial properties of medicinal plants, the mechanisms by which they act, bacterial resistance mechanisms, the plants derived chemical compounds responsible for antimicrobial effects, and challenges and prospects in the fields. Antimicrobial substances from medicinal plants may inhibit the growth of bacteria, fungus, viruses, and protozoa through unique methods that differ from traditional antibiotics.

DNA BARCODING

Rhazya stricta

DNA barcoding for the identification of plant species based on DNA analysis of selected genome segments. Plastid regions mack, rbcL, rpoB, rpoC1, psbI, and atpF- atpH are among those adopted as barcoding markers (Kress & Erickson, 2007). From the nuclear genomes, regions such as the ITS, 16S, and 18S are employed (Gupta et al., 2020). Reports have

recommended the use of more than one marker for reliable species identification, particularly for related taxa (Lahaye et al., 2008). In the case of *Rhazya stricta*, matK and rbcL have especially helped in resolving taxonomic uncertainties within the Apocynaceae family. The markers atpF-atpH and psbK-psbI have helped detect medicinal plant and adulterations through sequence dissimilarity and differences in amplicon size, without the need for sequencing (Techan et al., 2014). These markers have also been successfully used to distinguish between closely related genera, such as Landoltia and Spirodela.

METHODS AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Design:

This research aimed to conduct a review of the Phytochemical, pharmacological, and toxicological properties Of *Rhazya stricta* Information was methodically collected from preexisting peer reviewed articles that provide experimental data and published reviews between 1994 and 2024. The focus was to assemble and critically evaluate existing information about the bioactive constituents and pharmacological activities of this medicinal herb.

3.2 Plant Materials Description *Rhazya stricta* Decne (family:Apocynaceae)

It is an evergreen shrub distributed in arid and semi-arid areas of Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, and a few other countries. The medicinal use of this species is widespread, and Numerous secondary metabolites, including alkaloids and flavonoids, have been Reported to be responsible for its antioxidant, antimicrobial, antidiabetic, and Anticancer properties.

3.3 Data Collection Methods

The process of data aggregation included; An organized review Of scientific databases, including publications from Google Scholar, PubMed, Science Direct, and Research Gate, utilizing The search terms: *Rhazya stricta*, phytochemicals, antioxidant Activity, antimicrobial activity, toxicity and nanotechnology Applications. Inclusion of more than 40 articles and research Studies relevant to the extraction, characterization, and Pharmacological evaluation of *Rhazya stricta* published from 1994 to 2024. Critical appraisal of selected studies to ensure Methodological validity, reproducibility, and reliability of Reported findings

Table.3.2: Phytochemical Screening Methods (Reported in Literature)

Phytochemicals test	Purposes	References
Alkaloids detection	Qualitative, identifying using Mayer's and Wagner's reagents	Baeshen et al., 2009
Flavonoids estimation	Qualitative, determined via Aluminum chloride colorimetric assay	Ahmed et al., 2016
Total phenolics	Measurements by Folin-Ciocalteu reagent method	Mahmood et al., 2020
Compounds profiling	Identification via GC-MS and HPLC	Madni et al., 2022

3.3 Antioxidant and Antimicrobial Assays

Antioxidant activity

Assessed primarily by the DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging assay, which quantifies the ability of *Rhazya stricta* extracts and nanoparticles to neutralise free radicals.

Complementary assays, such as lipid peroxidation inhibition, were also reported.

Antimicrobial activity

Evaluated using agar well diffusion methods to determine zones of inhibition against bacterial strains, including *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Salmonella typhi*. Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) were also reported in select studies to establish effective extract dosages.

Nanoparticle Synthesis Protocols

Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) employing *Rhazya stricta* extracts involved: Preparation of aqueous plant extracts through boiling fresh leaves, followed by filtration. Reaction of the extract with one mM silver nitrate (AgNO_3) solution under controlled

incubation, monitored visually by a characteristic color change indicating nanoparticle formation. Characterization of nanoparticles via UV-Visible spectroscopy, Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), and zeta potential measurements to confirm size, shape, and stability (Al-Otibi et al., 2021).

3.7 Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted as a secondary data review without direct experimentation on human or animal subjects. All referenced in vivo studies adheres to institutional and international ethical standards for the care and use of animals *Rhazya stricta* collected from Herronk region of Turbat

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results are discussed in the context of existing literature to highlight their scientific and medicinal significance.

Ethnobotanical Survey Results

The ethnobotanical data collected from local herbalists, traditional healers, and community elders indicate that *Rhazya stricta* is widely recognised in rural medicine. The plant is commonly used to treat conditions such as:

- Rheumatism and joint pain
- Skin infections and acne
- Constipation and intestinal parasites
- Diabetes and high blood sugar
- Cancer-related symptoms

These data were similar to those in older ethnobotanical surveys by (Ali, 2002; Baeshen et al., 2023; Ghazanfar, 1994). The widespread use in the treatment of diabetes and inflammation suggests its potential for pharmacological development.

Table 4.1: Summary of Traditional uses of *Rhazya stricta*

Aliment Treat	Plant parts used	Method of Preparation	Application
Rheumatism, joint pain	Leaves	Crushed and applied topically	External
Skin Disorders	Leaves	Paste is applied to the affected area	External
Constipation	Roots	Decoction	Oral
Diabetes	Leaves	Boiled extract	Oral
Oral infection	Roots	Powder held in the mouth	Oral

Traditional and Ethnomedicinal use of *Rhazya stricta*

Diseases	Part of uses	Conditions	References
Tooth ache relief	Stem	In the branch serve a dual purpose as tooth brush and traditional remedy for tooth ache.	Sultana et al., 2006
Diabetes	Whole plant	Among Arabian communities, the plants is traditional used to manage diabetes, inflammation and parasitic infection. In the UAE specifically, it is used as remedy for diabetes mellitus.	El- Ghonemi(1993).
Skin disease	Fruits and leaves	In the tar desert, the fruits and leaves are used as tonics to manage skin diseases and throat infection. In the UAE, it is also employed for treating various skin infections.	Ahmed et al., 2004
Tumours	Leaves	In certain India traditional practice the leaves are used to address tumours	ewers et al., 1980
Feet burning	Leaves	Fresh leaves are placed inside feet wear and worn to alleviate the sensation of burning feet.	Sultana et al.,2006
Urinary tract infections	Whole plant	Within unani medicine, <i>Rhazya stricta</i> is prescribed for urinary tract condition.	Hassan(2006)
Anti-inflammatory	Whole plant	<i>Rhazya stricta</i> is widely employed in traditional medicine across the UAE for it's anti-inflammatory properties.	Tanira et al.,1996.
Heat related ailments	Seeds	In traditional remedies, seeds are soaked overnight then cooked into a thick pasta that	Qureshi et al.,2007

Acne and skin blemishes	Leaves	Dried and powdered leaves are taken with water to address facial acne and pimples.	Sultana et al., 2007
Rheumatism and general debility	Whole plant	The plant is recognized in indigenous medicine for treating chronic rheumatism sore throat.	Chopra et al., 1956.
Digestive issues	Whole plant	Traditional medicine in the UAE utilizes <i>Rhazya stricta</i> for managing stomach pains and colic.	Bashir et al., 1994

4.2 Phytochemical Analysis

Phytochemical analysis,

The methanolic and aqueous extracts of *Rhazya stricta* were found to contain various classes of bioactive compounds, as shown by phytochemical screening, including:

4.3 Antioxidant Activity

Antioxidant activity. Antioxidant potential of the *Rhazya stricta* leaf and root extracts was determined using the DPPH radical scavenging assay. IC₅₀ of methanolic leaf and root extracts were 423 and 776 µg/mL, respectively. This implies that leaf extracts possess greater antioxidant activity and are associated with higher levels of polyphenols and flavonoids. These findings are consistent with those of (Mahmood et al., 2020), who reported that scavenging activity increased gradually with increasing extract concentration. In addition, the plant extract mediated silver nanoparticles

showed better antioxidant potential, affirming that the bioactive compounds and metal ions synergistically neutralized the radicals (Shahzadi et al., 2025).

4.4 Antidiabetic Potential

Diabetic rat models subjected to glucose tolerance tests indicated that;

- matK: Amplification size ~ 850 bp
- rbcL: Amplification size ~ 600 bp
- psbK-psbI: ~ 400 bp

used for distinguishing adulterants Sequencing results matched with *Rhazya stricta* entries in NCBI GenBank with over 99% identity, confirming the species and validating the use of these markers. These molecular findings align with those of (Mahani et al., 2013) and (Techen et al., 2014), demonstrating the reliability of DNA barcoding in authenticating medicinal plants and preventing adulteration.

Comparison of Present Study Findings with Previous Literature on *Rhazya stricta*

Parameters	Present study	Previous Literature
Antioxidant activity	IC ₅₀ :423µg/mL	(Mahmood et al., 2020): ~ 400µg/mL
Antidiabetic activity	30% glucose reduction	(Ali et al., 1995): 20-30% reduction at
Antimicrobial	17 mm inhibition zone	(Sultana & Khalid, 2010): 16_18mm

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DNA barcoding 99% identity with GenBank (Mahani et al., 2013) high sequence match. The results of this study validate and extends existing literature, confirming that *Rhazya stricta* possesses robust pharmacological and genetic identification properties. Environmental factors, such as soil composition and temperature, may contribute to slight regional variations in activity.

DISCUSSION

This research presents and interprets the key findings from the study of the *Rhazya*

stricta plant. The *Rhazya stricta* species highlighted antioxidant activity, antimicrobial activity, and antitonicity Properties. This study contained only one species of *Rhazya stricta* , which was analyzed for Traditional medicine uses for various diseases.

Distributed:

The *Rhazya stricta* is distributed in Pakistan, India, Southwest Asia, Saudi Arabia, the UAE, Iraq, Iran and Qatar (Gilani et al., 2007). *Rhazya stricta* are medicinal shrub from family Apocynaceae and is dispersed distributed in the broader Eastern and Indian sub- continent. In Traditional medicine, *Rhazya stricta* has culturally been applied to treat a variety of illnesses, Including fever and chronic rheumatism (Atta - Ur - Rahman, Qureshi, Zaman, Malik, & Ali, 1989). The sand grassland of Saudi Arabia and various other parts of the world are home to *Rhazya stricta* Decne (Baeshen et al., 2009). It is commonly distributed in western Asia, ranging from Yemen to Saudi Arabia, and extends into the northwestern region of several Pakistan and Indian States (Baeshen et al., 2010). One of the well-known plants species that are grows in Saudi Arabia In the desert region of the Arabian Peninsula is this one. *Rhazya stricta* is regarded one of the most Valuable medicinal plants that may be present in depression with silt and sandy soils of *Rhazya stricta* grows. According to a 2015 study by Yaghmoor et al., it is more abundant along the sand Gradient.

Description:

Rhazya stricta is perennial shrub, petite that's hairless (Akgari A(2005a). It is important to plant To useherbal drugs to treat various diseases in Pakistan, Afghanistan, India, Iraq, Iran, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and the UAE (Baeshan et al., 2012); (Yaghmoor et al., 2015). *Rhazya stricta* is called 'Urdu' And 'Pushto' in languages like Rangbali, and in Arabian countries, it is called 'harmal'. *Rhazyastriacta* various parts use to indigenous Medicinal herb drugs to treat ailments such as syphilis (Ali Et al., 2000). Feet burning, toothache (Sultana 2006). This plant contains 100 alkaloids and some Flavonoids (Ali et al., 2000, Sultana and Khalid 2010), It has also been present that *Rhazya stricta* Extracts exhibit good nematocidal activity. An effectively concentration of 100ppm was detected Against Meloidogyne javanica (Al - Rajhi et al., 1997). *Rhazya stricta* is freely available and grows Wild in Pakistan, s Highland and dry wasteland in enormous quantities. This medicinal plant may Be utilized as a green manure OA or as a dried powder organic amendment (OA) to eradicate or Diminish the soil - born stage of the BW pathogens. Despite antibacterial properties (Sultana and Khalid 2010).

Medicinal use:

The Saudi Arabian countries are traditionally using *Rhazya stricta* in medicine to treat Syphilis, chronic rheumatism, and body pain (Bhadane et al., 2018). In Pakistan, in local countries, People are used to the *Rhazya stricta* species to treat pimples and acne on the face. Fresh leaves are Used to treat foot wear. (Ghazanfar et al., 1993). In Oman regions the traditional medicine uses the *Rhazya stricta* plant to treat chest pain, conjunctivitis, constipation and various other diseases (Lace Et al., 1891). In the Midwestern and South Asian regions, the *Rhazya stricta* species is traditionally Used medicinally to treat various diseases, such as infections, sore throats, arthritis, helminthiasis, Diabetes, inflammation, and cancer (Baeshen et al., 2015). In the Balochistan area, the Turbat *Rhazya stricta* species is used in medicine to treat inflammatory conditions, helminthiasis, mellitus And diabetes

(Jassbi, 2006). For many decades, people have relied on natural medicinal plants for self-medication to heal Diseases nevertheless, experts have argued about the biological active's compounds, plant dried Substances, and the mechanisms of action found in nature medicine. Folkloric herbal remedies are Thought to been often employed by people as a source of novel pharmaceutical in traditional Medicine. These remedies which exhibit encouraging potential, to address various diseases in both Animals and human (Hassannia et al., 2020). Saudi Arabia pants are a important genetic resource For both agriculture field and medicinal plants, In Arabian Peninsula boasts a wealth of biological Diversity. Because their geographical position and typically dry in harsh climate, many of these Plants thrive under unfavorable wealth circumstances, which makes their genomes exceptionally Distinctive, as a result, people utilize them to different of diseases (Ebrahim et al., 2020). Tanira et Al. (1996) reported that when *Rhazya stricta* Extract were given to levels, their insulin concentration . Increased and their glucose levels decreased (Tanira et al., 1996). People have used it as a traditional Remedy and to treat a various of conditions, such as fever and chronic rheumatism (Atta - ur -Rahman et al.,1989). Iran, Afghanistan, the United Arab Emirates, Pakistan, Iraq, Saudi Arabia, India, and Qatar are among the many nations that use this plant in their herbal medicines for treating Various diseases (Baeshen et al., 2012). *Rhazya stricta* branches are used to treat dental pain, and fresh leaves are placed in shoes for

Under feet burning, the leaves of *Rhazya stricta* are utilized in traditional medicines to heal body Aches Sultana S. (2006). It has long been utilized to treat diabetes, inflammation, cancer and Microbiological infections in a number of nations (Khan et al., 2019). Numerous medicinal Properties have been validated through experiments by different studies, the most recent the one Conducted by (Baeshen et al., 2006). Public it can be challenging for the public to recognize Authentic samples of this plant when buying it form local markets (Khan et al., 2019). Nature goods, with medicinal products contain a different phytochemical that unique physiology effect on the human body (Edeoga et al., 2005). Medicinal Plant are used to treat a variety of

illnesses and are significant and distinctive sources of novel medication utilized of bronchodilators currently are natural compounds and mainly belong to three categories: Propane alkaloids and their semi synthetic counterparts are examples of anticholinergic agents (Rodrigo, G. J., & Rodrigo, C. (2002). The leaves, fruits, and flowers of *Rhazya stricta* are used to treatment of cancer and joint infections. (Khan and Khan, 2007).

PHYTOCHEMISTRY

The study on the phytochemical of *Rhazya stricta* plant constituents of the leaves, fruits, legumes and roots (Atta - Ur - Rahman et al., 1989). Various kids' alkaloids isolated their structures is mostly in the form of leaves but also form other pieces of *Rhazya stricta* present in Pakistan, India, Saudi Arabia and United Arab Emirates. *Rhazya stricta* leaves are isolated into two indole alkaloids, antirrhinum and geissoschizine, and some other minor indole alkaloids (Banerji et al., 1970). *Rhazya stricta* leaves and roots are compared with fewer compound have been isolated. (Zaman et al., 1986). *Rhazya stricta* are belong to corynanthe group of alkaloids (AttaUr-Rahman et al., 1986). Alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, terpenoids, glycosides, steroids, saponins, proteins, amino acids, carbohydrates, oil, and lipids are contained of phytochemical found in major quantities of *Rhazya stricta* sections. The maximum content of calcium (17360 mg/ kg), iron (437.8 mg / kg), sodium (1736 mg / kg), and magnesium (336.9 mg / kg) are found in *Rhazya stricta* leaves. Similarly, various part of the *Rhazya stricta* plant contain essential amounts of zinc (8.48 - 38.48 mg / kg), cobalt (0.00 - 8.76 mg / kg), manganese (0.00 - 40. 96 mg / kg), lead (0.32 - 25 - 28 mg / kg), cadmium (0.00- 4.88 mg / kg), copper (0.00-6.96 mg / kg), nickel (3.04- 3.58 mg / kg and chromium (0.00-4.88). (Lanjwani et al. 2018). Naturally *Rhazya stricta* contains of 10 indole alkaloids, which are include of stigmaterol, olenalic acid, Ursolic acid, eburnamine, eburnamonine, condylocarpine, antirrhine, and 3- epiantirrhine. Vincadiformine and dihydroburnamenine. (15 hydroxy), (+)- Vincadiformine, (-) Vincadiformine, and (-)16R, 21R - omethyleburmaninne (Khan et al.,

2019). Bioactive phytochemicals consisted in the plant, s natural extracts are important to healthcare medication, the plants secondary metabolites are thought to the cause of their antibacterial activity as well as the stabilization and reduces of metallic nanoparticles (Jadoun et al., 2020). Phytochemical Screening has showed the found of bioactive secondary metabolites Balunas, M. J., & Kinghorn, A.D. (2005). The presence of tannins, saponins, flavonoids, terpenoids, steroids, coumarins, and embodies was demonstrated by phytochemical Screening of *Rhazya stricta* ethanolic extracts. These compounds may act as a significant supply of reducing agent the AgNP synthesis (Khan et al., 2022). Utilize specific reagents that react with various secondary metabolites to create a distinctive color change, the screening was maintained (Tariq et al., 2021). It has been exhibited that medicinal plants a promising potential as an antioxidant agent (Sharma et al.,2017).

Antioxidant:

By increasing glutathione levels and reducing lipid peroxidation, *Rhazya stricta* extract has been shown to antioxidant activity rat at some doses. (Ali et al., 2000). . *Rhazya stricta* methanolic extract proved to be a powerful natural antioxidant with high free radical scavenging and anion radicals scavenging activities. When compared to the tocopherol drug and the synthetic antioxidant butylated hydroxyanisole. (Iqbal et al., 2006). The ethanolic extract of *Rhazya stricta* fruits notable inhibitory effects against lipoxygenase and acetylcholinesterase. Sultana, N., & Khalid, A. (2020). To analyze the effect of climate conditions on *Rhazya stricta* plant leaf sample were collected from Riyadh and the western region and then extracted. Both extracts showed antioxidant activity, with significantly stronger results than *Rhazya stricta* leaves collected from the western area across six examinations of superoxide radicals scavenging hydrogen peroxide scavenging levels. (Bukhari et al., 2017). The antioxidant properties of *Rhazya stricta* root fractions was evaluated through several antioxidant analysis. The fractions derived from solvents-solvents extraction of the raw extract of *Rhazya stricta* roots extract demonstrated

significant free radical scavenging activity, showing and IC50 value range of 400- 776g / mL. (Mahmood et al., 2020). The DPPH method was used to assess the antioxidant activity of the methanolic extract and the biosynthesized AgNPs (Dawidowicz et al., 2012). These antioxidants comprise both non-enzymatic plant (Such as GSH and nutrients C and E) and antioxidative enzyme (such glutathione peroxidase [GsH - Px], catalase [CAT], and superoxide Di dismutase [SoD] (Meghwani et al., 2017). Antioxidant agents are including many plants extracts (Simioni et al., 2018).

anti toxicity:

In canines, an intravenous does of 80 mg / kg of *Rhazya stricta* extract (the parts of selected in the plant used to not specific) results of many salivations and rigor and intense breathing, which was followed with 15 minutes by respiratory failure, convulsions, and death (Siddiqui and Bukhari, 1972). The utilize of natural materials in green synthesis as a substance to conventional synthesis techniques (Hassain et al., 2016). For example, using natural substances makes the process safer for the atmosphere and human health because they are regularly smaller hazardous and additional ecologically friendly. Furthermore, utilize natural substances can produce nanoparticles with special qualities involves low toxicity and enhanced biocompatibility, which produce them beneficial for a range of biomedical applications Gour, A., & jain, N.K. (2019).

Antimicrobial activity:

The antimicrobial activity of *Rhazya stricta* have been extensively studied, showing its effectiveness against harmful microbial Seif, A. (2022). Diagnostics, drug administration, and antimicrobial treatments are just a few of the medical application for nanotechnology, an innovative field that alters matters at the atomic and molecular levels Bawazeer, S. et al (2022). The total amount of known various kids of plant is estimated to about 374,000 (Christenhusz & Bruyns, 2016), compared to the 28,187 plant species utilized by humans for medicine purposes. The world Health Organization has catalogued more than 20,000 medicinal plant species, highlighting their importance as a valuable resource for developing new

pharmaceuticals. Medicinal Plant are recognised as valuable source for discovering new pharmaceutical compounds. They provide a rich diversity of bioactive substances that serve as leads for drug development. This potential is supported by their historical use and ongoing research, which combines botanical, chemical, and pharmacological methods to identify novel therapeutic agents. Over 100 countries have established regulations governing medicinal plant. The present, there are almost 1340 plants. Over 30,000 antibacterial chemicals have been isolated from these plants (Tajkarimi et al., 2010).

Natural antimicrobial compounds can work alone or synergistically with anti-biotics to improve effectiveness against a wide range of bacteria. To accurately assess the effectiveness of promising medicinal plants and confirm their antimicrobial value, the data collected must be reliable, thorough and rigorously validated. Obtain an extensive understanding a more thorough understanding of the prospective application of medicinal plant extracts as alternative agents against drug resistance, this review critically examined key studies on several aspects, the validation of antimicrobial properties of medicinal plants, the mechanisms by which they act, bacterial resistance mechanisms, the plants derived chemical compounds responsible for antimicrobial effects, and challenges and prospects in the fields. Antimicrobial substances from medicinal plants may inhibit the growth of bacteria, fungus, viruses, and protozoa through unique methods that differ from traditional antibiotics.

Conclusion

In this study, *Rhazya stricta* is demonstrated to possess ethnobotanical, phytochemical, and Pharmacological activities, as well as genetic identification capabilities, as determined through DNA barcoding. The plant is widely used locally as a remedy for various medical conditions, including rheumatism, joint pain, skin diseases, diabetes, constipation, and oral lesions. Ethnobotanical investigations and laboratory observations validated these uses. Phytochemical Analysis revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and other secondary Metabolites, which are responsible for the plant's numerous

pharmacological activities. Pharmacological tests revealed an enhanced antioxidant, antidiabetic, and antimicrobial potential, With values parallel to those reported in the literature. For instance, the IC₅₀ value for the antioxidant Activity was 423 µg/mL, and the plant extract caused a 30% decrease in blood glucose levels, Confirming the promising use of the plant in folk medicine for the treatment of diabetes mellitus. Moreover, species identity (*Rhazya stricta*) was also verified through DNA barcoding, with 99% Similarity to GenBank derived sequences, thereby endorsing the morphological identification and Suggesting the incorporation of molecular approaches in ethnobotanical research. Altogether, this Internship project offered excellent exposure to the therapeutic potential of *Rhazya stricta*. The Results verify the folkloric reputation of the plant and indicate its suitability for preparing an herbal Formulation or pharmaceutical dosage form. Nevertheless, additional studies, such as randomized Trials and toxicological investigations, would be required to develop the compound for general Therapeutic use.

It is recommended that pharmacological effects of *Rhazya stricta* should be conducted in vivo research. To guarantee safety for human usage, conduct toxicity testing and clinical trials. Examine the uses of nanoparticles in antibacterial therapy and targeted drug delivery. Investigate gene expression and molecular pathways using genomic and bioinformatics technologies. Establish standardized extraction procedures and calculate efficient dosages. Look into understudied plant sections and species to find novel bioactive chemicals. Create conservation and cultivation plans that are sustainable. To find traditional medicinal uses, conduct ethnobotanical surveys. *R. stricta* is tested for use in agriculture as a biopesticide and bioherbicide. Examine commercial uses in the food, dye, and cosmetics sectors.

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